

CORTISOL: CENTRAL REGULATOR IN NEURONAL PLASTICITY

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SUMMARY

This essay investigates the role of cortisol as a **central regulator of neuronal plasticity**, considering physiological, molecular, and hormonal aspects. Neuronal plasticity is a continuous and dynamic process, essential for the adaptation of the nervous system throughout life. We explore how cortisol, acting as a transcription factor, modulates the expression of key genes that directly affect neuronal metabolic pathways, including **ATP production** in mitochondria, energy homeostasis, and the activity of neurotransmitters such as **glutamate** and **GABA**. We highlight specific genes modulated by the cortisol-GR complex and how this regulation impacts processes such as mitochondrial biogenesis, protection against oxidative stress, and the maintenance of synaptic plasticity. This study proposes an integrated view of how gene regulation and cortisol action are key to **synaptic remodeling, excitatory-inhibitory balance**, and stress adaptation, providing a solid foundation for understanding brain resilience and plasticity under adverse conditions.

Keywords: cortisol, neuronal plasticity, transcription factor, glucocorticoids, metabolic genes, neuroplasticity, energy metabolism, neuronal resilience, homeostasis, synapses.

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INTRODUCTION

Neuronal plasticity refers to the ability of the nervous system to adapt, modify, and maintain its structures and functions in response to environmental and internal demands. It is a continuous process that permeates all facets of neuronal life, ensuring its **viability** even in adverse situations (Kandel et al., 2021). In this context, **cortisol**, a glucocorticoid hormone, stands out as an essential regulator of neuronal plasticity, acting as a **transcription factor** that directly influences gene expression and facilitates the functional and structural adaptation of neurons over time (McEwen, 2017).

This essay examines the specific genes modulated by the cortisol-glucocorticoid receptor complex (cortisol-GR) and how this modulation affects neuronal metabolic pathways. Understanding these mechanisms is crucial to elucidate how cortisol contributes to neuronal plasticity and the brain's resilience in the face of challenges.

1. ROLE OF CORTISOL AS A TRANSCRIPTION FACTOR IN NEURONAL PLASTICITY

Cortisol is a **lipophilic** hormone capable of freely crossing cell membranes, binding to **glucocorticoid receptors (GR)** in the cytoplasm of neuronal cells. This binding forms a **hormone-receptor complex** that translocates into the nucleus, acting as a **transcription factor** by binding to **glucocorticoid-responsive elements (GREs)** in DNA. This complex modulates the expression of several genes that influence neuronal metabolic pathways, directly impacting **synaptic plasticity** and **neuronal resilience** (Sapolsky, 2000).

1.1 GENES MODULATED BY THE CORTISOL-GR COMPLEX AND METABOLIC IMPACT

PGC-1A (PEROXISOME PROLIFERATOR-ACTIVATED RECEPTOR GAMMA COACTIVATOR 1-ALPHA)

- **Function:** Transcriptional coactivator that regulates **mitochondrial biogenesis** and energy metabolism by influencing genes involved in oxidative phosphorylation.
- **Cortisol-GR Modulation:** The cortisol-GR complex increases PGC-1 α expression, promoting the production of functional mitochondria and enhancing neuronal ATP production capacity.
- **Metabolic Impact:** Elevation of PGC-1 α improves neuronal metabolic efficiency, meeting the energy demands essential for synaptic plasticity (Wareski et al., 2009).

GENES OF ANTIOXIDANT ENZYMES (E.G., SOD2 - SUPEROXIDE DISMUTASE 2)

- **Function:** Protect cells from oxidative damage by neutralizing reactive oxygen species (ROS).
- **Cortisol-GR Modulation:** Increases the expression of antioxidant genes, strengthening cellular defenses against oxidative stress.
- **Metabolic Impact:** Reduces oxidative stress while maintaining mitochondrial integrity and efficiency in ATP production, which are essential for healthy neuronal function (Du et al., 2009).

GLUT3 (GLYCOSE TRANSPORTER TYPE 3)

- **Function:** Main glucose transporter in neurons, responsible for capturing glucose for energy metabolism.
- **Cortisol-GR Modulation:** Regulates the expression of GLUT3, adjusting glucose uptake according to the energy needs of the cell.

- **Metabolic Impact:** Increases glucose availability by enhancing ATP production via glycolysis and providing energy for synaptic processes (Vannucci et al., 1998).

MITOCHONDRIAL RESPIRATORY CHAIN GENES (E.G., COX1 - CYTOCHROME C OXIDASE SUBUNIT 1)

- **Function:** Essential components of the electron transport chain in the mitochondria, crucial for the production of ATP via oxidative phosphorylation.
- **Cortisol-GR Modulation:** Influences the expression of genes in the respiratory chain, affecting the efficiency of ATP production.
- **Metabolic Impact:** Optimizes mitochondrial capacity to produce energy, meeting high metabolic demands during intense synaptic activity (Du et al., 2009).

2. STRUCTURAL PLASTICITY AND BLOOD FLOW

The maintenance of **neuronal plasticity** depends on constant **structural renewal**, including the replacement of synaptic proteins and **cytoskeletal** components. Although neurons are in the **G0 state**, they are able to maintain their functionality due to continuous **protein turnover** (Katzman et al., 2015). **Incessant blood flow** is essential in this process, ensuring the delivery of **oxygen, glucose, and amino acids**, as well as the removal of metabolic waste (Attwell & Laughlin, 2001).

Blood flow also facilitates the delivery of **neurotrophic factors**, such as **BDNF (Brain-Derived Neurotrophic Factor)**. The relationship between cortisol and BDNF is complex; elevated cortisol levels, as in chronic stress, can reduce BDNF expression, while physiological levels can have contextual modulating effects (Smith et al., 1995).

3. BALANCE BETWEEN AROUSAL AND INHIBITION: CORTISOL'S ROLE IN SYNAPTIC REGULATION

Synaptic plasticity involves changes in the efficiency of synapses. Cortisol regulates the **balance between arousal and inhibition**, ensuring that synaptic activity remains within an optimal range (McEwen & Morrison, 2013).

- **Glutamate and Excitatory Plasticity:** Cortisol regulates the expression of genes responsible for **glutamate receptors**, especially the **NMDA receptor**, which is essential for **long-term potentiation (LTP)** (Popoli et al., 2012).
- **GABA and Neuronal Inhibition:** Cortisol modulates the expression of genes related to **GAD65/67 (Glutamate Decarboxylase)**, enzymes that convert glutamate into **GABA**, the main inhibitory neurotransmitter. This ensures proper inhibition of neural circuits (Verkuyk & Joëls, 2003).

4. PLASTICITY AND INSTANTANEOUS ATP PRODUCTION

Neuronal plasticity depends on the continuous production of **ATP**. Cortisol regulates the balance between ATP consumption and production in neurons by modulating genes that affect mitochondrial functionality and glucose availability. This regulation avoids the **energetic breakdown** that would compromise neuronal plasticity (Karst et al., 2010).

4.1 PROTECTION AGAINST OXIDATIVE STRESS

Cortisol increases the expression of **antioxidant enzyme genes**, such as **SOD2**, protecting neurons from oxidative damage. This maintains mitochondrial integrity and efficiency in ATP production (Du et al., 2009).

5. THE CORTISOL PARADOX: BENEFITS AND LIMITS

While cortisol plays a key role in **neuronal adaptation and maintenance**, its impact depends on a **delicate balance**. Under conditions of **chronic stress**, elevated cortisol levels can have detrimental effects, such as **dendritic atrophy** and **reduced neurogenesis** in the hippocampus (Lupien et al., 2009). High concentrations of cortisol can reduce **BDNF** expression, compromising synaptic plasticity.

At physiological and well-regulated levels, cortisol is essential for the **maintenance of plasticity**, contributing to the **resilience** and **adaptation** of neural networks (Joëls & Baram, 2009). Understanding the mechanisms by which cortisol transitions between beneficial and harmful effects is crucial for the development of therapeutic interventions.

CONCLUSION

Neuronal **plasticity** is a complex process that ensures the adaptation and survival of neuronal cells in the face of different challenges throughout life. Cortisol emerges as a central element in this dynamic, modulating the expression of key genes that influence neuronal metabolic pathways. Through the regulation of genes such as **PGC-1 α** , **SOD2**, **GLUT3**, and neurotransmitter-related enzymes, cortisol ensures **continuous ATP production**, protection against oxidative stress, and balance between synaptic excitation and inhibition.

Understanding cortisol's dual role in plasticity—its benefits at physiological levels and the potential harms in conditions of chronic stress—is critical to understanding the mechanisms of neural adaptation. This may open avenues for the development of interventions that protect the brain from the deleterious effects of **chronic stress** and promote **homeostasis**. Future research should deepen the understanding of the molecular mechanisms mediated by cortisol, aiming at therapeutic strategies that maximize its benefits and minimize its risks.

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